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CDR- Chain Reaction Dependent Nuclear Fission Reactor.

CIR- Chain Reaction Independent Nuclear Fission Reactor.

CDRs - chain reaction dependent reactors rely on chain reaction for their proper functioning, if chain reaction stops then the reactor also stops converting energy(nuclear energy into thermal energy), nuclear power plants using this type of reactors have been existed for years, nuclear fission of uranium 235 or plutonium or other fissile materials happens in this type of reactors realising a large amount of energy which can then be harvested using various methods.

CIRS - chain reaction independent reactors are a new type of nuclear reactor. the thing that makes these types of reactors different from current nuclear reactors (CDRs) is they don't need a fissile fuel to work, since they don't rely on nuclear fission chain reaction. how they work is external protons or alpha particles accelerated using the electromagnets coils in the vacuum tube until these protons attain certain kinetic energy of about a few mega electron volts (MEV), then this high energy proton is directed towards the nucleus of fuel (let's say uranium 238) splitting the uranium nucleus hence releasing a huge amount of energy which can be harvested using various methods.

MAIN

Nuclear energy has become the epitome of sustainable energy, we have been extracting nuclear energy for decades, the primary ways to extract nuclear energy is through fusion reactor or fission reactors each with its own advantages and disadvantages.

Nuclear fission reactors can be divided into two categories, Chain reaction dependent reactor (CDR) and Chain reaction independent reactor (CIR) for nuclear fission, we are already quite familiar with CDRs they have existed for years and are very useful for many purposes with their own advantages and disadvantages, CDRs rely on chain reaction for their proper functioning, if the chain reaction stops then the fission reactor also has to stop , but that's not the case for CIRs , CIR is the topic of this paper , it's a new type of fission reactor design that I came up with and developed for years.

The way CIR work is accelerated plasma with kinetic energy is targeted or bombarded towards a non-fissile high mass element core (eg Uranium 238) and the uranium atoms undergoes fission this process is repeated until every atom in core is fissioned, releasing heat which will be harvested for generating electricity. The kinetic energy of plasma depends on the material of core and contents of the plasma. For uranium 238 core and hydrogen plasma, protons with kinetic energy of 3.5-4 Mev is suitable to cause fission.

The important point to be noted here is CIR doesn't require fissile fuel to function, heavy elements from lead to 118 (Oganesson) which are stable and fissionable are suitable for CIRs. Since CIR doesn't rely on chain reaction, they are inherently safer than traditional nuclear fission reactors.

Advantages of CIRs (Chain Reaction Independent Nuclear Fission Reactor) over CSRs (Chain Reaction Dependent Nuclear Fission Reactor)

1) Critical Mass: Critical mass is the minimum mass of a fissile material needed for a sustained nuclear chain reaction in CSRs, the fissile material has to be of certain size, if the size of reactor core is less than a certain, the chain reaction will not be sustained.

CIRs: since CIRs don't rely on chain reaction, there is no limitation of critical mass or size, allowing the reactor core to be significantly smaller than a CSR reactor core.

2) Moderators and Reflectors: Moderators slow down high energy neutrons to a certain point that they are capable of sustaining chain reaction. Reflectors prevent neutron leakage from the reactor core. moderators and reflectors are large and bulky surrounding the reactor core

CIRs: Since CIRs don't rely on chain reaction Reflectors and Moderators are useless for CIRs, hence further reducing the size of reactor core.

3) scarcity of fuel: Uranium 235 which is used in CSRs is scarce, while uranium itself is abundant most of the uranium is U-238 about 99.27% and U235 is about 0.72% which further needs enrichment increasing cost of fuel.

CIRs: The basic idea of CIRs reactor is to avoid chain reaction, hence uranium 238 or other Non-Fissile but Fissionable elements are preferred as fuel for CIRs, since they are abundant in nature, the fuel for CIRs are more accessible and abundant.

4) Safety and Robustness: CSRs use U-235, various external elements like plane crash, tsunamis, explosions, etc can compromise the safety features of CSRs causing uncontrolled chain reaction which eventually leads to major accidents.

CIRs: U-238 which can be used in CIRs requires Fast Moving Neutrons for nuclear fission and they cannot sustain chain reaction, so even after the nuclear reactor poses significant damage from external factors, the probability of uncontrolled chain reaction is extremely low. Hence CIRs are inherently safer than CSRs.

DESIGN AND WORKING

The design of CIRs is as follows,

A hollow circular tube with vacuum inside, the hollow circular tube is arranged such as it resembles a hollow torus. the tube is the place where sub-atomic particles are accelerated to kinetic energies of few electron volts, the particle loops inside the tube in circular motion with an increase in kinetic energy with each revolution, However the radius of the revolution of the particle also increases gradually, hence a magnetic field (described later) is used to provide centripetal force to contain the particle, In practical there will be millions of particles revolving around the centre, for theoretical simplicity I am considering a single particle .

As the particle reaches certain kinetic energy, the particle will collide with the nuclear core which contains the non-fissile but fissionable material (example: Uranium 238) each particle causes a nuclear fission to a nuclear core fuel element, and since CIRs does not rely chain reaction the neutron economy is less than 1.

Coil-2 is the arrangement of coils along the length of the circular tube, these coils turn on and off in a systematic rhythm with certain frequency, and the frequency oscillates between certain upper limit and a lower limit, as the coils turn on and off the electromagnetic force repels and attracts the particle which results in an increase in kinetic energy of the particle.

Coil-1 is the primary coil that produces magnetic field responsible for preventing the particle to escape due to increase in radius as the particle accelerates. This coil produces magnetic field the direction of which is represented by dot and cross marks in the diagrams, now when the particle revolves in the circular tube it experiences a centripetal force directed towards the centre which nullifies the increase in radius of the particle which is produced due to increase in the speed of the particle. The strength of this coil will be dependent of the instantaneous average velocity of all particles.

Feeder is the element that feeds particles into the vacuum chamber, A thermal system would be needed to extract the fission energy from the core and direct it to external systems where it would be turned into usable electrical energy.

The CIRs can be divided into two types (Type 1 and Type 2)

TYPE 1 CIRs: In type 1 CIRs the nuclear core and heat extraction unit is at the centre of torus and the accelerated particles has spiral path to the core, eventually hitting the core with enough kinetic energy that can cause nuclear fission of the nuclear fuel.

TYPE 2 CIRs: In type 2 CIRs the nuclear core is on the outer side of the torus, the advantage of this configuration is, the magnetic field at the centre of the reactor consumes less energy, in type 1 the coils had to produce strong magnetic field that fights with the centrifugal force to bring the particle near the core, but in type 2 since the nuclear core is outside , the magnetic coils have to produce comparatively lower strength magnetic field.

The image below depicts the path of particle which will bombard the nuclear core.

The image below depicts the arrangements of coils, electric and magnetic fields.

The image below is the design of type 2 CIR

